

From Agricultural Residue to Sustainable Value: Assessing Agro-Based Biopackaging Solutions for the Healthcare Sector

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Abstract

The mismanagement of agricultural byproducts and healthcare packaging waste poses significant environmental challenges, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and pollution. Biopackaging from agricultural residues offers a promising solution, but its adoption in healthcare remains limited due to stringent regulatory requirements and gaps in research and development. Sustainability mandates, consumer demand, and environmental concerns are creating opportunities for innovation. This paper systematically reviews biopackaging applications in healthcare, as well as biofilms and sustainable fiber extraction methods to enhance material properties and sustainability. Findings show that existing healthcare biopackaging is mostly made of paper, cardboard, or bioplastics from virgin sources, with no examples from agricultural residues. Biofilms can be categorized into polysaccharide-, protein-, or polyester-based films, and require additives like plasticizers and nanofillers to compete with synthetic films. Enzyme- and bacterial-retting are the most scalable sustainable fiber extraction methods, while newer methods such as microwave- and ultrasound-assisted methods are emerging at lab scale. Ultimately, choices of biofilm, additives, and processing methods must be tailored to feedstock,

material availability, and application. Advancing biopackaging in healthcare at scale requires further research and innovation to reduce costs, develop tailored composites, enhance supply chain efficiency, establish supportive policies, and enable circular end-of-life solutions.

Introductions

Agriculture and its related industries produce vast amounts of waste. One study estimates that six globally important crops produce approximately 3.7 billion metric tonnes of residue each year (Bentsen et al., 2014). This agricultural residue consists of materials that remain on the fields after crops have been harvested such as rice straw, wheat straw, rice husk, and corn stover (Adhikari et al., 2018). Further up in the food supply chain, agro-based industries like food processing produce substantial amounts of additional waste in the form of peels, seeds, pits, pulps, press cakes, among others. With a growing population and increasing food demand, the resulting rise in agricultural and agro-industrial waste raises significant concerns (Freitas et al., 2021).

The vast majority of agro-based residues are landfilled or burned – practices that have severe environmental repercussions (Adhikari et al., 2018). Landfilling organic waste leads to the production of methane, a greenhouse gas significantly more potent warming potential than carbon dioxide (El-Fadel et al., 1997). Along with methane, open-field burning – a practice particularly prevalent in regions such as South and Southeast Asia – also releases additional harmful pollutants including particulate matter (e.g. PM2.5), carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, ammonia, carcinogens such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, and other toxic compounds (Emilie, n.d.). Together, this poses serious impacts on both climate change and public health.

In parallel, urban activity is driving another waste crisis in the form of escalating packaging and consumer waste. Recent data from industry analyst Smithers Packaging mentions that the global packaging market was worth \$914.7 billion in 2019, which is an 8.4% increase from 2015. This reflects the magnitude of the packaging industry, deemed to compoundly grow by 2.3% each year (Stark & Matuana, 2021). Though often short, the lifecycle of packaging contributes to depletion of scarce resources, pollution of air and water, and accumulation of solid waste (Selke, 2022). An often overlooked contributor to this crisis is the healthcare industry. While statistics

vary, a meta-analysis of medical waste in 78 countries revealed an average of 2.04 kg of health care waste (HCW) generated per hospital bed per day – a number that is expected to increase by 2- 3% per year (Kaposi et al., 2024). Inadequate HCW management means that a lot of this waste is landfilled or incinerated, leading to public health and environmental impacts (*Health-Care Waste*, n.d.).

A promising solution to both agricultural and healthcare waste crises is the use of biopackaging made from agricultural byproducts in the healthcare sector. This approach not only diverts waste from landfills and reduces waste incineration, but also offers significant environmental benefits. For instance, the application of starch in bioplastics reduced greenhouse gas emissions by 80% and non-renewable energy use by 60% (Abe et al., 2021). Beyond environmental advantages, transforming agricultural waste into biopackaging materials creates additional revenue streams for farmers and agro-processors. By assigning economic value to residues, a tangible incentive to collect and sell this biomass rather than resorting to harmful disposal methods is created. This practice fosters **localized circular food systems and enhances rural livelihoods**, while contributing to a more sustainable healthcare sector.

While the adoption of agro-based biopackaging is gaining momentum in industries like food and beverage, its integration into the healthcare sector remains limited. These industries are governed by stringent regulatory standards that prioritize sterility, durability, and material stability, posing challenges to the introduction of innovative packaging solutions. However, recent directives emphasizing sustainability and circularity are creating favorable conditions for the exploration of eco-friendly healthcare packaging alternatives (Ashiwaju et al., 2023; Saini, 2022) – particularly for secondary packaging that does not come in direct contact with the medicine or medical device (Forcinio, 2024). Although biopackaging has begun to enter the healthcare sector under these favorable conditions, adoption is limited and key challenges persist including finding sustainable processing methods and compatible bio-based films that help fulfill environmental sustainability goals and healthcare packaging standards (Cordeiro et al., 2025).

This research aims to bridge this knowledge gap by:

- 1. Identifying bio-based packaging utilized globally in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and medical device sectors**
- 2. Assessing sustainable processing methods and identify suitable bio-based films that enable bio-based packaging to align with healthcare industry packaging standards, particularly in terms of barrier properties, durability, and sustainability**

Methods

This research adopts a systematic literature review approach, following the reporting guidelines set out in the PRISMA Statement for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Liberati et al., “The PRISMA Statement for Reporting Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses of Studies That Evaluate Health Care Interventions.”). The eligibility criteria of the reviewed literature were as follows: (i) pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and medical device industry focus (ii) interventions related to sustainable production and application biopackaging made from agricultural residue, (iii) outcome of production process (e.g. sustainable processing method, use of biofilm) or application of biopackaging described and (iv) empirical data evaluated. Although the primary focus is the healthcare sector, research on sustainable processing methods and biofilms drew on literature from other sectors, as sector-specific data was not particularly relevant to this aspect of the study. Literature reported in or translated to English was included, with the search conducted in English only. Studies focusing on (bio)packaging produced from virgin packaging was not included as the focus of the study is on circular packaging solutions.

The literature review was conducted over the period of 1 month from July 2025 to August 2025, with one person as a data extractor. Search fields included free text, considering key words relating to the target population, intervention and outcome. The following terms, among others, were used for the literature search: ‘secondary packaging healthcare,’ ‘biopackaging healthcare sector’, ‘bio-based secondary packaging healthcare sector,’ ‘biopackaging agricultural residue healthcare,’ ‘bio-based packaging healthcare’, ‘bio(-based)packaging pharmaceuticals’, ‘bio(-based)packaging nutraceuticals’, ‘sustainable fiber extraction methods’, ‘sustainable (pre)processing methods biopackaging’, ‘biopackaging production methods’, and ‘biofilms packaging’. The search strategy was adapted according to the databases.

Studies were not excluded in the analysis for quality reasons if the eligibility criteria were met, and the limitations and possible biases in such studies are reported in the limitations section. The analysis grouped studies into three categories based on the focal research area: (i) biopackaging applications in the healthcare industry; (ii) sustainable production or processing methods of biopackaging; (iii) biofilms that can complement base materials of biopackaging. Biopackaging applications were summarized in evidence for subsequent analysis. Sustainable processing methods prioritized techniques that minimize chemical inputs, reduce water consumption, and enable circularity, while maintaining fibre quality. Bio-based films that enhance mechanical, barrier, antimicrobial, and durability properties of biopackaging were considered. Each category was analyzed independently before being integrated to identify cross-cutting insights.

The search strategy was applied to the following databases, registers, websites, organisations to locate peer-reviewed studies: SAGE Senior Ambassador Reports, SpringerLink, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, JSTOR, Taylor & Francis Group, World Health Organization Library, Wiley Online Library, MDPI, Springer Nature Link, and the The Royal Danish Library database. Literature searches were made across these platforms on various dates ranging from 10 July 2025 to 10 Aug 2025. No publication date restrictions were applied, given the irrelevance of timing to the research question. References cited by relevant literature were also investigated for additional articles. Grey literature including biopackaging company websites were included if found relevant to the research question and if they fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

After removing any duplications, all selected articles were screened for relevance based on the title and abstract only. The full text of all relevant studies was then reviewed for final assessment by one independent data extractor. Relevant information, including study bibliographic information, study design and objectives, existing applications of biopackaging in the healthcare sector, sustainable biopackaging pre-processing methods, suitable biofilms to complement biopackaging, and additional relevant information was extracted and tabulated in evidence tables for analysis. Captured data was then analyzed through thematic coding to uncover key themes.

Results

There is an increasing focus on sustainability within the healthcare packaging sector driven by the mounting environmental crisis, COVID-19, consumer preferences, and regulatory mandates

like the The European Parliament and of the Council 2018a (Cazzaniga, 2025; Cordeiro et al., 2025). This is supported by the growing amount of literature pertaining to medical packaging generally, of which some focus on environmental dimensions, that is paralleled with a rise in publications on bioinspired packaging and designs ((Cazzaniga, 2025; Cordeiro et al., 2025).

The sustainability transition in healthcare packaging has taken various forms including reducing plastic, lightweighting, designing for recyclability, adopting renewable fibre-based options, rightsizing (cube efficiency) and minimizing the number of packaging sizes and configurations, and improvement of shipping effectiveness (Deore et al., n.d.; Forcinio, 2024). While still in its infancy stages, innovations span across primary and secondary packaging. In the following section, the current applications of biopackaging in health care, innovations of bio-based films to complement biopackaging, and sustainable processing methods of biopackaging based on the systematic literature review will be elaborated upon.

Current Context: Bio-Based Biopackaging Applications in the Healthcare Industry

This section will summarize current applications of biopackaging in the healthcare sector, with a particular focus on secondary packaging applications. Findings can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Applications of Biopackaging in the Healthcare Industry

Product	Company	Product Category	Material Sources	Properties & Features	Applications	Impact
MedEco Bio-Com pounds	BioVox	Medical grade bioplastics	Renewable & recyclable raw materials	Properties for each product line can be found here	Medical and laboratory devices and packaging	Reduce the CO2 footprint by up to 85%; biodegradable; recyclable; energy efficient processing; deforestation-free plantation sources; human rights integrated throughout supply chain

One Clean Carton	Colbert Packaging	Solid bleached sulphate (SBS) paperboard	Chemically processed virgin fiber with no mechanical pulp in a middle ply; water based inks by Huber; water based coatings by Cork Industries, Inc., and water based adhesives supplied by Capital Adhesives	Strong sheet that performs well, with no jamming or tearing in the production run; low migration, low odor, and low V.O.C	Secondary packaging of pharmaceuticals	100% fibre-based; reduces production waste and use of raw materials; avoids any retained solvents/amines
Rondo Solutions	Körber	Cardboard insert & cut-out partition blanks	100% cardboard monomaterial from sustainable wood fiber sources	Dimensionally stable, high-quality design, pleasant to the touch, patented topload process, cost-efficient production, variable combinations possible	Secondary packaging of pharmaceuticals (e.g. syringes, ampoules, needles)	100% compostable; circular
All-paper packaging	Vetter Pharma	All-paper carton packaging	Wood fiber sources	Single- and multi-unit formats	Secondary packaging configurable for vials, syringes, and delivery devices	Sustainable all-paper construction

EcoVial	Innovative Bottles	100% Plant-based Prescription Vials with Cap	Luminy® PLA made from sustainably sourced sugarcane	High-grade material finish, durable, premium look and feel	Primary packaging of medicines, i.e. Vials	100% Plant-Based PLA; compostable & plastic-Free; FDA-compliant; child-resistant; moisture-proof; reduces greenhouse gases by 32%; uses 42% less energy than polypropylene
Bioplastics PLA-Premium	ADBioplastics	Bioplastic PLA-Premium	Virgin PLA and ADBio PLA+ additives, derived from natural and environmentally friendly sources such as corn, sugarcane, or beet	Improved mechanical properties compared to regular PLA by up to 7× including toughness and impact resistance; enhances barrier properties for oxygen and water vapor by 25–30% over standard PLA; doubles flowability (vs. only 30% in virgin PLA); maintains transparency similar to PET	Bottles, trays (hinged-lid thermoforming), blisters, single dose, ampoules	Compostable; produced from natural sources

NonOilen®	PANARA	Bio-based plastics	Biopolymers, primarily produced from biomass; additive from renewable raw materials	Biocompatible; can be produced to be hard, strong, or brittle; flexible and sufficiently tough; dimensionally stable up to a temperature of 120 °C; retains its properties during use and storage; possible repeated use; can be printed on	Packaging, medical devices	100% biodegradable; fully compostable; biodegradable; made exclusively from polymers from renewable sources
Amecop	Renogroup	Paper-based tray	FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) and/or PEFC (Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Schemes) certified wood fiber sources	High industrial processing speeds: from 100 to 350 cartons/tray per minute, depending on its configuration (single, multipack)	Secondary packaging of pharmaceuticals	100% biodegradable; fully compostable; responsible sources; made exclusively from paper
Ecoslide-RX	Keystone Folding Box Co	Paperboard blister pack, containing push button safety feature	100% recyclable paperboard	Consumer testing indicates it is “easy to open,” most cost-effective package of its kind in the market	Pharmaceutical packaging	Reduces need for plastic by 50 - 75%; passed CPSC protocol testing for child resistance with an F=1 rating; increases medication adherence to daily dosing
Innovative Development of Biodegradable	UNSW Mechanical and Manufacturing	Green healthcare packaging products	Biodegradable polymer polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), specially	Still in research and development phase	Applicable to markets such as drug delivery, pharmaceutical	Still in research and development phase

dable Healthcare Packaging Products	Engineering		fermented from canola oil		cal, diagnostics, and orthopaedics (still in research phase)	
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As evident, current applications of biopackaging in the healthcare industry consists primarily of paper or cardboard based packaging and biopackaging. Feedstock for the identified biopackaging applications primarily comes from conventional virgin sources, such as corn, bagasse, and sugarcane, with only a few companies (e.g. Ameco, BioVox) prioritizing environmentally responsible sources, such as materials from sustainably managed forests. None of the biopackaging used in healthcare currently uses agricultural residue or byproducts as feedstock, highlighting a clear gap and opportunity for innovation. That being said, the existing biopackaging products have key properties and features that make them applicable for the healthcare sector including biocompatibility, thermal stability, child-resistance, printability, barrier properties, processability, cost efficiency, ease of use, among others. Vials, cartons, blister packaging, and trays are the packaging components for which bio-based solutions have been explored. The impact of these current biopackaging applications in the healthcare sector focuses on reducing plastic waste, lowering carbon footprints, and enabling circularity. All in all, it is clear that biopackaging applications in the healthcare sector is still at its infancy stages, with room to grow - particularly in regards to the use of agricultural waste as feedstock as well as in the diversity of packaging applications. On the flip side, the existing cases of biopackaging applications in the healthcare industry shows the potential for growth in this field.

Biofilms to Complement Base Materials of Bio-Based Packaging

A key challenge in employing bio-based materials for the healthcare industry, particularly residue-based biomaterials, is ensuring that it meets industry requirements and policy compliance (Cazzaniga, 2025). While primary packaging is more highly regulated as it comes in direct contact with medication, secondary packaging is also faced with many requirements. Tamper evidence, child resistance, medicine protection, anticounterfeiting, serialization, clear

communication are some among other design features that secondary packaging must consider (Forcinio, 2024). Fibre-based materials often lack sufficient mechanical, barrier, printability, and durability properties to meet such compliance (Cordeiro et al., 2025). Bio-based films have thus gained key attention as a potential solution to enhance the properties of biopackaging to make them viable sustainable and competitive solutions.

Table 2 summarizes key findings related to bio-based films that can enhance properties of biopackaging, based on the systematic literature review. The main bio-based films can be divided into three broad categories: polysaccharide-based films, protein-based films, and polyester-based films. Each category and specific source material of the films have varied but overlapping properties that can potentially complement bio-based packaging for the healthcare industry.

Table 2: Bio-Based Films & Coatings

Bio-Film Material	Potential Sources	Properties Advantages	Limitations	Potential Reinforcements
Polysaccharide-Based Films				
Starch	Tapioca, potato, corn, wheat, cassava, rice, millets, kernel	Biodegradable, edible, oxygen barrier properties, non-toxic, good film forming ability, abundantly available, odorless	Low mechanical properties, poor tensile strength, poor moisture barriers, low thermoplastic activity, high water solubility, brittleness, retrogradation, limited thermal stability	Plasticizers (E.G. glycerin, sorbitol) to reduce brittleness and thermoplastic activity; waxes and lipids to increase the barrier, mechanical, and optical characteristics; natural antioxidants (e.g. organic acids, phenolic acids, terpenes and antibacterial compounds) to increase product stability, extend storage term, enhance sterility, barrier properties; cross-linking agents (e.g. glutaraldehyde, epichlorohydrin) to improve tensile strength; nanoclays (e.g. montmorillonite) or other nanofillers to improve barrier, mechanical and thermal properties; modifications (e.g. oxidation)

Cellulose & derivatives, nanocellulose, hemicellulose	Cotton, jute, wood, and agricultural waste like wheat straw, bagasse, bacteria, pineapple peel residue	Good mechanical properties, non-toxicity, renewable, biodegradable, lightweight, hydrophobicity (depends on biomass source), chemical stability, low cost Nanocellulose: excellent thermostability, barrier properties, flexibility, good biocompatibility, higher liquid absorption, mechanical and chemical resistance	Limited mechanical properties in high humidity, poor thermoplasticity, low elasticity	Nanofillers (e.g. PBTA/PLA/CNC (poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)/poly (lactic acid)/cellulose nanocrystals), PCL/CNC/ZnO (polycaprolactone/cellulose nanocrystals/zinc oxide), chitosan/LCNF (lignin with cellulose nanofibrils)) to achieve properties similar to petroleum-based polymers; Bio-based matrices (e.g. PLA, PHA, PHB, starch-based polymers, chitosan, alginate, soy protein)
Chitosan	Exoskeletons of marine insects and invertebrates such as arthropods, crustacean and cephalopod internal shells, as well as fungi cell walls	Excellent antimicrobial activity, biocompatible, non-toxic, hydrophilicity, stable structure, tough, durable, flexible, hard to tear, selective gas permeability, good water barrier	Inadequate mechanical properties, poor water resistance, brittleness, weak intermolecular forces of the polymer structure, weak barrier properties	Cross-linkers; Nanofillers and other bioactive compounds (e.g. polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), or essential oils (e.g., apricot kernel)) to reduce water vapor transmission rate, enhance antimicrobial activity, and improve hydrophobicity and tensile strength (e.g., 94% increase with oils)
Pectin	Fruits and vegetables such as mulberry leaf extract	Biocompatible, biodegradable, excellent thickening and gelling properties, satisfactory mechanical properties	Hydrophilic, poor water vapor and gas barrier properties, generally low mechanical strength, satisfactory	Nanoparticles (e.g. crystalline nanocellulose (CNC) and nanoclay) can enhance mechanical and barrier properties; Blensa (e.g. fatty acids, HPMC, gelatin, alginate, chitosan, soy protein isolate, starch,

			mechanical properties	carboxymethyl-gellan, and various plant-derived bioactive compounds) to improve functional properties
Alginate	Brown seaweeds (Phaeophyceae)	Excellent adhesion and filming capabilities, non-toxic, biodegradable, homeostatic character	Hydrophilic, inadequate mechanical properties, poor water resistance	Blends (e.g. chitosan and essential oils like lemongrass, garlic, tea tree oil) to improve their antimicrobial and antioxidant properties; Nanoclays (e.g., graphene oxide) to enhance mechanical properties, thermal stability, and moisture barrier performance; Plasticizers (e.g. glycerin, sorbitol, polyethylene glycol (PEG), fructose, and sodium lactate) to improve mechanical characteristics and modify water vapor permeability
Pullanan	Black yeast like the fungus Aureobasidium pullulans	Colorless, are transparent, have no taste or odor, are heat stable, and have high oil and oxygen impermeability	Poor strength (breakability), brittleness, hydrophilic nature, absence of bioactive function	Co-Blending (e.g. functional polymers, bioactives, and nanofibers obtained from plant or microbial sources) can improve properties; Plasticizers (e.g. glycerol) can improve film characteristics; Nanofillers (e.g. copper sulfide nanoparticles (CuSNP), silver nanoparticles, nano-TiO ₂ , ZnO, cellulose nanofibers, and lysozyme nanofibers) can significantly improve film strength, flexibility, stiffness, and other physical and functional properties; Blends (e.g. Pullulan with carrageenan, alginate, carboxymethyl cellulose, chitosan, casein, starch, or whey protein isolate) can improve mechanical and barrier properties.

Lignin	Wheat straw	Natural UV-blocking ability, improves flame retardancy, offers favorable thermal stability, has good antioxidant properties, biodegradable	Compromised tensile strength	Functionalization (e.g. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)-functionalized lignosulfonate hybrids); Nanoformulation (e.g. lignin with copper oxide nanoparticles); Blends (e.g. soy protein) can significantly improve properties of lignin biofilms
Protein-Based Films				
Soy	Soybean seeds	Renewable, biodegradable, biocompatible, good gas barrier properties in low moisture conditions, flame retardancy, thermal stability, antimicrobial properties, transparent, flexible	Poor inherent cohesion, weak interfacial interactions, high affinity for water due to their hydrophilic nature, poor water vapor/moisture barrier properties, brittle, lack high mechanical performance, and exhibit heat instability or allergenicity	Plasticizers (Glycerol, polyethylene glycol (PEG), sucrose, sorbitol, and triethanolamine), Nanofillers (Graphene, zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles, silicon dioxide nanoparticles, nanoboron nitride, cellulose nanofiber (CNF), and micro-crystalline cellulose (MCNC)), blends (pectin, dendritic tannin acid, hyperbranched polysiloxanes, and other biopolymers)
Gelatin	Connective tissue, skin, and bone of animals	High intermolecular binding potential, and higher mechanical properties than polysaccharide- and fat-based films, transparent, smooth, flexible, ease of processing	Low thermal stability, weak mechanical properties, low water vapor barrier, brittle in humid environments, lack inherent antibacterial, antioxidant,, and UV-shielding properties	Plasticizers (Glycerol, sodium alginate, sucrose, polyethylene glycol (PEG), and sorbitol), Nanofillers (Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC), Laponite clay, nano-ZnO, copper-doped zinc oxide nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles, essential oils, and aminoclay), blends (PMC, pectin, chitosan, starch, hyperbranched polyester, cardanol derivative, polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), and essential oils)

Gluten	Wheat and wheat flour	Renewable, biodegradable, biocompatible, strength, elasticity, plasticity, relatively water-insoluble, effective oxygen barrier properties	Brittle and difficult to handle, allergenicity, deterioration with age, processing difficulties, inadequate water vapor barriers when combined with plasticizers especially in humid environments	Plasticizers (Glycerol, ethanolamine, fatty acids (lauric, stearic, oleic acids), octanoic and palmitic acids, dibutyl phthalate, and tartrate), blends (polysaccharides, lipids (e.g., beeswax, paraffin, fatty substances), or other compatible proteins)
Whey	Milk protein, typically derived from cheese processing	Biodegradable, film transparency, gloss, excellent oxygen barrier performance	Low water vapor barrier properties, high sensitivity to moisture, poor mechanical strength, moderate gas barrier	Nanofillers (Zein nanoparticles, melanin, AgNPs), blends

Polyester-Based Films

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)	Bio-monomers like lactic acid, derived from renewable natural resources such as cornstarch, tapioca, or sugarcane	Strong, durable, melt-processable, and exhibits good drape, UV resistance, low water uptake, stiffness, tensile strength, optical clarity	Brittle, rigid, may not be biodegradable under certain conditions	Plasticizer (Glycerol), Nanofillers (Cellulose nanomaterials (CNFs, CNCs), starch nanocrystals, clay, melanin, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), lignosulfonate (LS), copper sulfide nanoparticles (CuSNP), and TiO ₂ nanoparticles), Blends (polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT), starch, or various plant extracts)
Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)	Gram-negative bacteria (e.g. Azohydromonas, Burkholderia, and Cupriavidus)	Biodegradable, biocompatible, hydrolytic sensitivity, optically active, non-toxic, and generally stable under UV irradiation, good	Fragile when homopolymers and brittle due to high crystallinity, low nucleation density (causing splitting and cracking), instability	Plasticizer (Lignophenols, lubricants, and compatibilizers), Nanofillers (Cellulose nanocrystals and nanofibrils, carbon nanofibers, quasi crystals, graphene oxide, and various nanosheets), Blends (PLA, polymethacrylate, polyethylene

		mechanical and gas barrier properties, a high melting temperature, and high tensile strength, strong antimicrobial activity	at various temperature ranges	glycol (PEG), ethyl cellulose, starch, polypropylene (PP), agave fiber, or cellulose)
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Polysaccharide-based films are generally characterized by low or non-toxicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. It also allows efficient passage of carbon dioxide and oxygen and has high chemical reactivity (Martins et al., 2022). Moreover, some polysaccharides also have functional properties such as chitosan with good antimicrobial activity (Varghese et al., 2023) and lignin with natural UV-blocking ability (Bian et al., 2021). However, polysaccharide-based films often fall short in their hydrophobic nature which leads to poor water resistance. On its own, these films can also often have low mechanical properties, brittleness, and low elasticity or tensile strength (Bangar & Siroha, 2023; Martins et al., 2022). Reinforcements such as nanoclays, essential oils, or bioactive compounds further improve water resistance, stability, and antimicrobial performance (Bangar & Siroha, 2023; Martins et al., 2022). Integration of polysaccharide in bio-films for biopackaging could help address regulatory requirements in healthcare packaging.

Protein-based films show strong gas barrier properties, making them useful for oxygen and contamination control in healthcare packaging (Bangar & Siroha, 2023; Donkor et al., 2023a; Reichert et al., 2020; Selvam et al., 2025). Each type of protein-based film exhibits unique qualities. For example, gelatin films have reasonable mechanical properties while maintaining smoothness, flexibility and transparency (Selvam et al., 2025). However, protein films are hydrophilic, brittle, and moisture-sensitive, restricting performance under variable storage conditions - particularly humid conditions (Reichert et al., 2020; Selvam et al., 2025). Reinforcement with plasticizers (e.g., sorbitol), nanofillers (e.g., ZnO, CNCs), or blends with polysaccharides improves toughness, hydrophobicity, and antimicrobial properties (Athanasopoulou et al., 2024; Bangar & Siroha, 2023; Li et al., 2021; Mihalca et al., 2021; Ortega et al., 2022a). With these enhancements, protein-based films are promising solutions to provide a protective layer for healthcare biopackaging, though poor water resistance may remain as challenges.

Polyester-based films like PLA and PHAs are closest to petroleum-based plastics in durability, clarity, and processability, making them highly relevant for healthcare packaging (Bangar & Siroha, 2023). PLA provides strength, UV resistance, and optical clarity but is brittle and not always biodegradable outside industrial composting (Hussain et al., 2024; Selvam et al., 2025; Şomoghi et al., 2025). PHAs are more broadly biodegradable and offer antimicrobial and barrier properties, though production costs remain high (Selvam et al., 2025; Şomoghi et al., 2025). Both can be strengthened with nanofillers or blended with starch, cellulose, or other biopolymers (Şomoghi et al., 2025). While economic feasibility remains a barrier, PLAs and PHAs have strong potential to offer a practical route to sustainable healthcare packaging.

Overall, bio-based films must be reinforced with other bioactive compounds, nanoparticles, and plasticizers to enhance their properties and make them competitive with other synthetic films, while meeting more of the regulatory environmental requirements for healthcare packaging.

Sustainable Processing Methods of Agri-Based Biopackaging

Although the shift to bio-based packaging is intended to reduce environmental impacts relative to petroleum-based packaging, conventional production methods for biopackaging can themselves be environmentally harmful (Dam & Bos, 2004). Therefore, integrating sustainability across the entire lifecycle of bio-based packaging is important to ensure it is a holistically green solution. One of the first and critical steps in the production of biopackaging is fibre extraction of the feedstock material, most often done through a process called retting. This involves separating and extracting fibers from the non-fibrous and woody tissues of the crops. Various retting processes can have harmful environmental impacts, particularly in relation to chemical usage, water pollution, and energy usage (Rahman et al., 2023). This section summarizes key findings on the sustainability of common fibre extraction methods, with particular attention to approaches and innovations that reduce environmental impacts while preserving fibre quality.

Water retting has historically been one of the most widely used methods for fibre separation, as it produces strong and fine fibres. However, this process is slow and highly polluting, since anaerobic bacterial fermentation releases foul odours and generates large volumes of wastewater rich in organic compounds (Lee et al., 2020). Studies have shown that retting ponds often exceed environmental quality standards, making wastewater treatment essential (Lee et al., 2020).

Seawater retting – using water from the sea instead of ground or surface water– can reduce freshwater consumption relative to regular water retting (Zhang et al., 2008). Although, both methods are still considered to be unsustainable as they require lengthy processing times and cause high levels of contamination. Recent innovations such as osmotic retting and ribbon retting have been developed to shorten retting duration and reduce water usage. These modified approaches show promise in producing fibres of good quality, while reducing environmental burdens (Ali et al., 2015; Banik et al., 2003; Lee et al., 2020).

Dew retting, which relies on natural fungal activity in the soil to separate and extract plant fibers, is a lower-cost and less polluting alternative to water retting (Lee et al., 2020). Although, the yield quality produced from dew retting is inconsistent and highly dependent on local climate conditions which can be a big barrier, particularly for the healthcare sector in which consistency in quality is critical (Forcinio, 2024; Lee et al., 2020). **Mechanical extraction methods** such as decortication, on the other hand, are less dependent on environmental factors but generally produce coarser fibers than other methods. They also require more energy and equipment, which increases costs and may create secondary pollution concerns (Mudoj et al., 2021; Rahman et al., 2023).

Chemical retting processes provide greater control and faster retting times compared to biological methods, but they introduce significant sustainability challenges. Chemical use often leads to heavily contaminated wastewater with high chemical oxygen demand, while also resulting in reduced tensile strength and discoloration of fibers (Lee et al., 2020; *Retting Process of Some Bast Plant Fibers and Its Effect on Fibre Quality*, n.d.). Research into recycling chemicals and treating wastewater through methods such as electrocoagulation has helped reduce such impacts (Boinpally et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the high cost and environmental hazards of chemical retting continue to limit its application in sustainable fibre production.

Enzymatic retting has emerged as one of the most promising eco-friendly alternatives. It operates under mild conditions, significantly reduces retting time, and avoids the use of harsh chemicals (Lee et al., 2020; *Retting Process of Some Bast Plant Fibers and Its Effect on Fibre Quality*, n.d.). Enzymes such as pectinase break down fibre-binding components, while chelators like EDTA can be added to enhance efficiency by weakening calcium-dependent structures (Lee

et al., 2020). Although enzymatic retting can sometimes reduce fibre strength if over-applied, careful process control can produce fibres of comparable quality to water-retted fibres (Lee et al., 2020). High enzyme cost remains a barrier to industrial adoption, but advances in enzyme formulation and microbial co-cultures are improving both efficiency and affordability of the process (Lee et al., 2020).

Other innovative methods are also being explored to increase sustainability. **Steam explosion (STEX)** offers an effective pretreatment that reduces chemical usage and improves retting efficiency (Jiang et al., 2018). When combined with enzymatic retting, STEEX has been shown to enhance fibre quality while lowering energy use and wastewater generation (Lee et al., 2020). **Bacterial retting** is another environmentally preferable approach, with life cycle assessments showing 20–25% lower environmental impacts compared to thermochemical retting (Fu et al., 2024). Furthermore, bacterial retting wastewater can be recycled, making the process more resource-efficient and circular in nature (Fu et al., 2024).

Table 3: Fibre Extraction Methods

Method	Strengths	Weaknesses / Environmental Impacts	Key Notes / Innovations
Water retting	Produces strong, fine fibres	Slow; foul odours; highly polluting; wastewater exceeds standards	Seawater retting reduces freshwater use; innovations like osmotic & ribbon retting reduce time & water use
Dew retting	Low-cost; less polluting; eco-friendlier	Inconsistent fibre quality; climate-dependent; unsuitable for high consistency demands	Limited by variability, esp. for healthcare packaging
Mechanical (decortication)	Independent of climate; faster than biological methods	Produces coarser fibres; high energy/equipment needs; secondary pollution	Trade-off between reliability and fibre quality
Chemical retting	Fast; controlled process	Produces contaminated wastewater; reduced fibre strength & discoloration; costly	Chemical recycling & wastewater treatment help, but still unsustainable
Enzymatic retting	Eco-friendly; mild conditions; shorter retting	High enzyme costs; risk of fibre weakening if over-applied	Advances in enzyme formulation & microbial cultures improving

	time; avoids harsh chemicals		efficiency & affordability
Bacterial retting	20–25% lower environmental impact vs. thermochemical; wastewater recyclable	Slower than chemical; still scaling	Promising circular and resource-efficient method
Steam Explosion (STEX)	Reduces chemical use; improves efficiency; enhances fibre quality	Requires energy input; currently hybrid stage with enzymatic retting	Combination with enzymatic retting shows strong potential
Hybrid/assisted (ultrasound, microwave, subcritical water)	Shortens retting time; reduces chemicals	Early stage; mostly lab-scale; high costs	Future innovation pathway, still experimental

Despite these advances, no single method achieves optimal results across all criteria of fibre quality, retting time, environmental impact, and cost (*Retting Process of Some Bast Plant Fibers and Its Effect on Fibre Quality*, n.d.). Traditional water and chemical retting methods are more unsustainable due to pollution and high amounts of inputs required, while dew and mechanical methods produce inconsistent fibre quality or use high amounts of energy. Enzymatic and bacterial retting appear most promising for future large-scale applications, as they balance efficiency with environmental performance. Ongoing research into emerging hybrid and assisted techniques – such as ultrasound, microwave, or subcritical water methods – offers further opportunities to shorten retting times and reduce chemical use, though these currently remain largely at laboratory scale (*Extraction of Biopolymers from Nature and Their Characterization - Biopolymers for Water Purification - Wiley Online Library*, n.d.). It should be noted that research on this topic is scarce and should be further investigated.

Discussion & Future Directions

It is clear that there is immense potential for growth of the bio-based packaging sector, shown by the growing number of research papers on the topic, policies released pertaining to this as well as market projections, among others. In the US alone, for instance, the biobased packaging and bottles sector has a marginal growth projection of 1.9% through 2028 and contributes approximately \$541,000,000 of direct value added and employment to the economy (Daystar et

al., 2021). This shows the potential of the biopackaging sector to not only create an environmental impact alongside profitability, but also to stimulate national economic growth. Biopackaging produced from agricultural residues presents an additional opportunity to maximize environmental impact by reducing greenhouse gas emissions from land use change and diverting organic waste from landfills, while not affecting food security by displacing food crops (Symons, n.d.-a).

While enabling policies, consumer demand, and market forces are opening avenues for the growth of bio-based packaging – particularly agri-waste-based materials – the research, innovation, and development required to meet stringent industry standards remain limited (Kossalbayev et al., 2025). As a result, most bio-based packaging solutions are still confined to the laboratory scale. Among the few real-world applications, bio-based films are the most prevalent (Debeaufort, 2021).

Many challenges lie ahead to scale the adoption of bio-based and agri-waste based packaging in a sustainable manner, particularly within the medical sector. Ensuring costs are competitive with existing packaging solutions is one of the major challenges. Since bio-based packaging – particularly those made from residue feedstocks – relies on immature, specialized technologies and is generally produced at lower volumes, fixed production costs remain high and economies of scale are limited (Selvam et al., 2025). This makes it difficult for biopackaging to compete with non-renewable packaging, at least in the short run. With cost being a major factor influencing purchasing decisions in the medical industry, methods to lower costs are critical (Penati, 2025). Technological progress, use of agricultural residue as feedstock, and creation of cost-effective composites will be essential to enhance competitiveness of biopackaging (Selvam et al., 2025).

Another major challenge is closing the performance gap between biopackaging and conventional packaging. Currently, most bio-based packaging solutions underperform compared to their non-renewable packaging counterparts in terms of thermal, mechanical and barrier properties (Donkor et al., 2023a; Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Selvam et al., 2025). They also generally have lower resistance to extreme weather conditions, particularly humid conditions (Donkor et al., 2023a). While important for most packaging applications, these properties are especially

important for packaging in the medical sector. Therefore, development of composite, multi-layer packaging with improved and comparable properties to alternatives will be critical for the application and scaling of bio-based packaging (Donkor et al., 2023a; Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Sahil Panjabrao et al., 2025; Varghese et al., 2023). Tailored composites would be needed based on feedstock material and desired properties (Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Oboturova et al., 2024). Growing bodies of research on biocomposites highlights the novelty and potential of these materials (Ortega et al., 2022b).

Produced by a nature-based, heterogeneous and perishable resource, that is biomass, biopackaging also confronts various supply chain challenges - from ensuring sufficient feedstock supply to logistics of transporting raw feedstock to scaling up green processing of biomass to securing markets for the products (Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Oboturova et al., 2024). It is therefore important to comprehend unique crop cycles and properties in order to develop effective supply management strategies, tailored green processing methods, and tailored biocomposites to bring out desired qualities in the packaging material (Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Oboturova et al., 2024). However, scaling of such tailored methods still remains a challenge for which solutions have to be explored (*Agro-Food Waste Valorization for Sustainable Bio-Based Packaging*, n.d.). On the demand side, consumer education and marketing on the favorability of biobased packaging and its benefits can play an important role in boosting demand, among other solutions like corporate engagement (Debeaufort, 2021; Wellenreuther et al., 2022).

Apart from the supply chain challenges, there exists another barrier to wide scale adoption of biopackaging which is lack of sufficient policy support and an integrated knowledge base. Financial incentives and procurement mandates are required, especially in the initial stages, to enhance price competitiveness of biopackaging (Kossalbayev et al., 2025). Alongside this, clear standards and labels are important (Symons, n.d.-b). To promote biopackaging from agricultural residue and byproducts, further policy support will be required due to additional barriers of production and application. This may take the form of feedstock-specific adjustments in areas such as labelling, standards and taxation, for instance (Selvam et al., 2025). Along with integrated and holistic policy support, there is a need to integrate and comprehend disparate scientific knowledge on the topic of biopackaging to propel its research and development to meet industry standards of packaging in the medical sector (Debeaufort, 2021).

Lastly, limited waste management infrastructure and systems poses a challenge to sustainable end of life disposal and circularity of biopackaging (Symons, n.d.-b; Versino et al., 2023). Currently, many certified compostable packaging never actually reaches industrial composting sites due to inadequate collection, mis-sorting or a lack of facilities (Kossalbayev et al., 2025). Proper sorting and disposal, clear product and disposal instruction labeling, along with appropriate industrial composting facilities are required to ensure circularity of biopackaging (Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Oboturova et al., 2024; Ortega et al., 2022b). This requires investment in both consumer education, design considerations and waste management infrastructure (Kossalbayev et al., 2025). Another interesting approach suggested is to build fully integrated production systems (i.e., biorefineries) in which different products from raw materials, by-products, and residues from one process are nearby biopackaging upcycling or recycling facilities to reduce waste generation, transportation costs, and emissions (Kossalbayev et al., 2025; Ortega et al., 2022b).

Despite challenges, biopackaging still presents a huge opportunity and has huge potential for growth (Debeaufort, 2021; Selvam et al., 2025). Bio-based materials are expected to stay as relevant sources of environmentally friendly packaging (Donkor et al., 2023b). The scaling of this solution and its transferability to the medical sector, however, will require filling research, development, and process gaps identified above which are summarized below:

- **Cost & Production Efficiency:** Advance materials and manufacturing processes to lower production costs and achieve economies of scale.
- **Performance & Functionality:** Develop biopackaging composites with thermal, mechanical, and barrier properties on par with conventional packaging.
- **Supply Chain & System Integration:** Optimize feedstock management, logistics, and integrated biorefinery approaches to reduce waste and maximize value.
- **Policy & Market Support:** Strengthen incentives, standards, and corporate engagement to drive adoption and consumer awareness.
- **Circularity & End-of-Life Solutions:** Invest in composting facilities, sorting campaigns, and circular packaging design to ensure sustainable end of life solutions.

Conclusion

The parallel agricultural and medical packaging waste crises demand innovative solutions. Bio-based packaging made from agricultural residues or byproducts has emerged as a potential means to tackle two crises with one stone, by transforming agricultural waste into sustainable packaging for the medical sector. While biopackaging holds immense potential for growth and application in the medical sector, various barriers prevent its widespread production and adoption. Solutions towards two specific gaps in innovation are explored in this report: bio-based films to enhance properties of biopackaging and green fibre extraction methods to enhance the sustainability of bio-based packaging.

Various bio-based films can be added to base layers of biopackaging to improve its properties for application in the medical sector. These films can be categorized into three types: polysaccharide-based films, protein-based films, and polyester-based films. Most nature-based films must be reinforced with plasticizers, nanofillers, cross-linking agents, or other materials to effectively enhance properties of biopackaging. Tailored compositions of bio-based films should therefore be developed for each biopackaging solution, considering the feedstock material and type of packaging among other factors.

In terms of sustainable fibre extraction or retting processing methods, innovations are still scarce with no silver bullet solution. However, research points to the fact that enzyme or biological retting processes may be the most eco-friendly methods currently applicable at scale, while newer methods such as ultrasound and microwave assisted retting methods are also emerging as other green alternatives.

While solutions are emerging to enhance properties and sustainability of biopackaging, various challenges still stand in the way of its widespread growth and transferability to the medical sector – demanding further research and development. Future efforts must focus on 1) lowering the cost and enhancing the production efficiency of biopackaging, 2) developing tailored composite biopackaging materials to achieve improved properties for medical sector application, 3) exploring methods to effectively develop and integrate biopackaging into medical packaging supply chains, 4) creating enabling policies to stimulate demand and competitiveness of biopackaging, and 5) creating design, infrastructure, and behavior change solutions to enable

circularity of biopackaging. With these gaps filled, biopackaging has immense potential to solve both the crises of agricultural and medical packaging waste at scale.

References

- Abe, M. M., Martins, J. R., Sanvezzo, P. B., Macedo, J. V., Branciforti, M. C., Halley, P., Botaro, V. R., & Brienzo, M. (2021). Advantages and Disadvantages of Bioplastics Production from Starch and Lignocellulosic Components. *Polymers*, *13*(15), Article 15.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13152484>
- Adhikari, S., Nam, H., & Chakraborty, J. P. (2018). Chapter 8—Conversion of Solid Wastes to Fuels and Chemicals Through Pyrolysis. In T. Bhaskar, A. Pandey, S. V. Mohan, D.-J. Lee, & S. K. Khanal (Eds.), *Waste Biorefinery* (pp. 239–263). Elsevier.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63992-9.00008-2>
- Agro-Food Waste Valorization for Sustainable Bio-Based Packaging*. (n.d.). Retrieved September 23, 2025, from <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/54997>
- Ali, M. R., Kozan, O., Rahman, A., Islam, K. T., & Hossain, M. I. (2015). Jute Retting Process: Present Practice and Problems in Bangladesh. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*, *17*(2). <https://cigrjournal.org/index.php/Ejournal/article/view/3212>
- Ashiwaju, B. I., Orikipte, O. F., Fawole, A. A., Alade, E. Y., & Odogwu, C. (2023). A Step toward Sustainability: A Review of Biodegradable Packaging in the Pharmaceutical Industry. *Matrix Science Pharma*, *7*(3), 73. https://doi.org/10.4103/mtsp.mtsp_22_23
- Athanasopoulou, E., Bigi, F., Maurizzi, E., Karellou, E. I. E., Pappas, C. S., Quartieri, A., & Tsironi, T. (2024). Synthesis and characterization of polysaccharide- and protein-based edible films and application as packaging materials for fresh fish fillets. *Scientific Reports*, *14*(1), 517. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-51163-y>

- Bangar, S. P., & Siroha, A. K. (Eds.). (2023). *Biopolymer-Based Films and Coatings: Trends and Challenges*. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003303671>
- Banik, S., Basak, M. K., Paul, D., Nayak, P., Sardar, D., Sil, S. C., Sanpui, B. C., & Ghosh, A. (2003). Ribbon retting of jute—A prospective and eco-friendly method for improvement of fibre quality. *Industrial Crops and Products*, *17*(3), 183–190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0926-6690\(02\)00097-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0926-6690(02)00097-3)
- Bentsen, N. S., Felby, C., & Thorsen, B. J. (2014). Agricultural residue production and potentials for energy and materials services. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, *40*, 59–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2013.09.003>
- Bian, H., Chen, L., Dong, M., Wang, L., Wang, R., Zhou, X., Wu, C., Wang, X., Ji, X., & Dai, H. (2021). Natural lignocellulosic nanofibril film with excellent ultraviolet blocking performance and robust environment resistance. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, *166*, 1578–1585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.11.037>
- Boinpally, S., Kolla, A., Kainthola, J., Kodali, R., & Vemuri, J. (2023). A state-of-the-art review of the electrocoagulation technology for wastewater treatment. *Water Cycle*, *4*, 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watcyc.2023.01.001>
- Cazzaniga, S. (2025). Medicine Packaging Legislation and Its Evolution According to Technological Innovation for Better Healthcare Support. In A. V. Penati (Ed.), *In-Home Medication: Integrating Multidisciplinary Perspectives in Design-Driven Pharma Practices* (pp. 37–55). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53294-8_2
- Cordeiro, A., Hussain, M., Ramachandran, T., Beemkumar, N., Kumar, R., Karthikeyan, A., Bupesh Raja, V. K., Thatoi, D. N., Mahapatro, A., Nanda, J., Prakash, C., & Patil, A. Y.

- (2025). Advancements in Packaging Materials: Trends, Sustainability, and Future Prospects. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-025-00586-4>
- Dam, J. E. G. van, & Bos, H. L. (2004). *The environmental impact of fibre crops in industrial applications*.
<https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/the-environmental-impact-of-fibre-crops-in-industrial-application>
- Daystar, J., Handfield, R., Golden, J. S., McConnell, E., & Pascual-Gonzalez, J. (2021). An Economic Impact Analysis of the US Biobased Products Industry. *Industrial Biotechnology*, 17(5), 259–270. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ind.2021.29263.jda>
- Debeaufort, F. (2021). Active biopackaging produced from by-products and waste from food and marine industries. *FEBS Open Bio*, 11(4), 984–998.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/2211-5463.13121>
- Deore, S. D., Gajmal, G. K., Jadhav, S. P., & Patil, D. M. (n.d.). Study of different methods of Pharmaceutical Packaging. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Cycle Research*, 0022.
- Donkor, L., Kontoh, G., Yaya, A., Bediako, J. K., & Apalangya, V. (2023a). Bio-based and sustainable food packaging systems: Relevance, challenges, and prospects. *Applied Food Research*, 3(2), 100356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2023.100356>
- Donkor, L., Kontoh, G., Yaya, A., Bediako, J. K., & Apalangya, V. (2023b). Bio-based and sustainable food packaging systems: Relevance, challenges, and prospects. *Applied Food Research*, 3(2), 100356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2023.100356>

El-Fadel, M., Findikakis, A. N., & Leckie, J. O. (1997). Environmental Impacts of Solid Waste Landfilling. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 50(1), 1–25.

<https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.1995.0131>

Emilie, C. (n.d.). *Field Burning* [Text/HTML]. World Bank. Retrieved August 10, 2025, from <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/en/989351521207797690>

Extraction of Biopolymers from Nature and Their Characterization—Biopolymers for Water

Purification—Wiley Online Library. (n.d.). Retrieved September 23, 2025, from

<https://onlinelibrary-wiley-com.ep.fjernadgang.kb.dk/doi/10.1002/9783527835904.ch2>

Forcinio, H. (2024). *Navigating Trends in Secondary Packaging*. 48, 22–25.

Freitas, L. C., Barbosa, J. R., da Costa, A. L. C., Bezerra, F. W. F., Pinto, R. H. H., & Carvalho

Junior, R. N. de. (2021). From waste to sustainable industry: How can agro-industrial

wastes help in the development of new products? *Resources, Conservation and*

Recycling, 169, 105466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105466>

Fu, Y., Gu, H., Wu, H. F., & Shi, S. Q. (2024). Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Bacterial and Thermochemical Retting of Hemp. *Materials*, 17(16), 4164.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17164164>

Health-care waste. (n.d.). Retrieved August 4, 2025, from

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/health-care-waste>

Hussain, M., Khan, S. M., Shafiq, M., & Abbas, N. (2024). A review on PLA-based biodegradable materials for biomedical applications. *Giant*, 18, 100261.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giant.2024.100261>

- Jiang, W., Song, Y., Liu, S., Ben, H., Zhang, Y., Zhou, C., Han, G., & Ragauskas, A. J. (2018). A green degumming process of ramie. *Industrial Crops and Products*, *120*, 131–134.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2018.04.045>
- Kaposi, A., Nagy, A., Gomori, G., & Kocsis, D. (2024). Analysis of healthcare waste and factors affecting the amount of hazardous healthcare waste in a university hospital. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, *26*(2), 1169–1180.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-024-01890-1>
- Kossalbayev, B. D., Belkozhayev, A. M., Abaildayev, A., Kadirshe, D. K., Tastambek, K. T., Kurmanbek, A., & Toleutay, G. (2025). Biodegradable Packaging from Agricultural Wastes: A Comprehensive Review of Processing Techniques, Material Properties, and Future Prospects. *Polymers*, *17*(16), 2224. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17162224>
- Lee, C. H., Khalina, A., Lee, S. H., & Liu, M. (2020). A Comprehensive Review on Bast Fibre Retting Process for Optimal Performance in Fibre-Reinforced Polymer Composites. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, *2020*(1), 6074063.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6074063>
- Li, K., Jin, S., Zhou, Y., Luo, J., Li, J., Li, X., Shi, S. Q., & Li, J. (2021). Bioinspired interface design of multifunctional soy protein-based biomaterials with excellent mechanical strength and UV-blocking performance. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, *224*, 109187.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.109187>
- Martins, B. A., de Albuquerque, P. B. S., & de Souza, M. P. (2022). Bio-based Films and Coatings: Sustainable Polysaccharide Packaging Alternatives for the Food Industry. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, *30*(10), 4023–4039.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-022-02442-0>

- Mihalca, V., Kerezsi, A. D., Weber, A., Gruber-Traub, C., Schmucker, J., Vodnar, D. C., Dulf, F. V., Socaci, S. A., Fărcaș, A., Mureșan, C. I., Suharoschi, R., & Pop, O. L. (2021). Protein-Based Films and Coatings for Food Industry Applications. *Polymers*, *13*(5), 769. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13050769>
- Mudoi, M. P., Sinha, S., & Parthasarthy, V. (2021). Polymer composite material with nettle fiber reinforcement: A review. *Bioresource Technology Reports*, *16*, 100860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2021.100860>
- Oboturova, N., Povetkin, S., Nikulnikova, N., Lazareva, N., Klopova, A., Lyubchanskiy, N., Sukhanova, E., & Lebedeva, N. (2024). Upcycling agricultural byproducts into eco-friendly food packaging. *Potravinarstvo Slovak Journal of Food Sciences*, *18*, 185–206. <https://doi.org/10.5219/1949>
- Ortega, F., Versino, F., López, O. V., & García, M. A. (2022a). Biobased composites from agro-industrial wastes and by-products. *Emergent Materials*, *5*(3), 873–921. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42247-021-00319-x>
- Ortega, F., Versino, F., López, O. V., & García, M. A. (2022b). Biobased composites from agro-industrial wastes and by-products. *Emergent Materials*, *5*(3), 873–921. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42247-021-00319-x>
- Penati, A. V. (2025). Towards In-Home Medication: Medicinal Products as Daily Objects. In A. V. Penati (Ed.), *In-Home Medication: Integrating Multidisciplinary Perspectives in Design-Driven Pharma Practices* (pp. 1–34). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53294-8_1
- Rahman, M. M., Maniruzzaman, M., & Yeasmin, M. S. (2023). A state-of-the-art review focusing on the significant techniques for naturally available fibers as reinforcement in

sustainable bio-composites: Extraction, processing, purification, modification, as well as characterization study. *Results in Engineering*, 20, 101511.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2023.101511>

Reichert, C. L., Bugnicourt, E., Coltelli, M.-B., Cinelli, P., Lazzeri, A., Canesi, I., Braca, F., Martínez, B. M., Alonso, R., Agostinis, L., Verstichel, S., Six, L., Mets, S. D., Gómez, E. C., Ißbrücker, C., Geerinck, R., Nettleton, D. F., Campos, I., Sauter, E., ... Schmid, M. (2020). Bio-Based Packaging: Materials, Modifications, Industrial Applications and Sustainability. *Polymers*, 12(7), 1558. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12071558>

Retting process of some bast plant fibers and its effect on fibre quality: A review :: BioResources. (n.d.). Retrieved September 23, 2025, from <https://bioresources.cnr.ncsu.edu/>

Sahil Panjabrao, A., Hamid, Dash, K. K., Kathuria, D., Shams, R., Chavan, P., Mukarram, S. A., & Kovács, B. (2025). Sustainable 3D-Printed food packaging from agricultural waste: A review of materials, properties, and applications. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 22, 102061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2025.102061>

Saini, D. (2022, July 18). Sustainable Packaging Innovations and IP Trends: A Step towards a Greener Planet. *Sagacious IP*. <https://sagaciousresearch.com/blog/sustainable-packaging-innovations-ip-trends-step-towards-greener-planet/>

Selke, S. E. M. (2022). *Packaging and the Environment: Alternatives, Trends, and Solutions* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780203744550>

Selvam, T., Rahman, N. M. M. A., Olivito, F., Ilham, Z., Ahmad, R., & Wan-Mohtar, W. A. A. Q. I. (2025). Agricultural Waste-Derived Biopolymers for Sustainable Food Packaging:

Challenges and Future Prospects. *Polymers*, 17(14), 1897.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17141897>

Şomoghi, R., Mihai, S., & Oancea, F. (2025). An Overview of Bio-Based Polymers with Potential for Food Packaging Applications. *Polymers*, 17(17), 2335.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17172335>

Stark, N. M., & Matuana, L. M. (2021). Trends in sustainable biobased packaging materials: A mini review. *Materials Today Sustainability*, 15, 100084.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtsust.2021.100084>

Symons, D. J. (n.d.-a). *ENVIRONMENTAL & ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF BIOBASED PACKAGING*.

Symons, D. J. (n.d.-b). *ENVIRONMENTAL & ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS OF BIOBASED PACKAGING*.

Varghese, S. A., Pulikkalparambil, H., Promhuad, K., Srisa, A., Laurenza, Y., Jarupan, L., Nampitch, T., Chonhenchob, V., & Harnkarnsujarit, N. (2023). Renovation of Agro-Waste for Sustainable Food Packaging: A Review. *Polymers*, 15(3), 648.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15030648>

Versino, F., Ortega, F., Monroy, Y., Rivero, S., López, O. V., & García, M. A. (2023). Sustainable and Bio-Based Food Packaging: A Review on Past and Current Design Innovations.

Foods, 12(5), 1057. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12051057>

Wellenreuther, C., Wolf, A., & Zander, N. (2022). Cost competitiveness of sustainable bioplastic feedstocks – A Monte Carlo analysis for polylactic acid. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, 6, 100411.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2022.100411>

Zhang, L. L., Zhu, R. Y., Chen, J. Y., Chen, J. M., & Feng, X. X. (2008). Seawater-retting treatment of hemp and characterization of bacterial strains involved in the retting process. *Process Biochemistry*, 43(11), 1195–1201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2008.06.019>